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**Indian Ocean: Validation of the Hybrid Coordinate Ocean
Model**

by

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Contents

1	Model Setup	2
2	Model Results and Validation	4
2.1	Indian Ocean Surface Circulation	4
2.1.1	Bay of Bengal	4
2.1.2	Arabian Sea	5
2.2	Transport	5
2.2.1	Indian Monsoon Current	7
2.2.2	Southern Equatorial Current	7
2.2.3	Equatorial Jet	7
2.2.4	Great Whirl	7
2.2.5	Somali Current	7
2.2.6	Indonesian Throughflow	7
2.2.7	East Indian Coastal Current	7
2.3	Water masses	8
2.3.1	SST and SSS	8
2.3.2	Antarctic Ice	9
2.3.3	Vertical sections of the temperature and salinity	9
2.4	ENSO Events	16
3	Conclusion	19

Indian Ocean: Validation of the Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model

Belma B. Batlak

Abstract

The Indian Ocean is unique in that it is limited in the north by the Asian continent. One consequence of this geography is that the Arabian Sea is forced by intense, annually reversing monsoon winds. These strong winds force the ocean locally, and they excite propagating signals (Kelvin and Rossby waves) that travel large distances and affect the ocean remotely.

The southwest (SW) monsoon is normally observed from May to August/September, and the northeast (NE) monsoon is observed from October to January/February. In the Bay of Bengal large rivers discharges and heavy rainfall result in low salinity, while the Arabian Sea has no major rivers draining into it, but receives high-salinity water from the Red Sea and Persian Gulf.

We have implemented, validated and done 10 year simulation experiment forced by synoptic atmospheric data using the HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) not previously used for the Indian Ocean. The simulation results compare well to the observations and previous modelling work done on the Indian Ocean.

1 Model Setup

The Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) (Bleck, 2002) has been set up for the Indian Ocean and the Antarctic. HYCOM is a primitive equation, general circulation model with vertical coordinates that remain isopycnic in the open, stratified ocean. The isopycnal vertical coordinates smoothly transition to z-coordinates in the weakly stratified upper-ocean mixed layer, to terrain-following sigma coordinates in shallow water regions, and back to z-level coordinates in very shallow water. This new hybrid formulation allows for better representation of different dynamical regimes such as in the surface mixed layer, the deep ocean, and the coastal and shelf regions. It is a significant upgrade of the original Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM).

The minimum grid distance in the model domain is 14 km, sufficient to resolve the larger mesoscale features. The Red Sea and Persian Gulf are included; the western boundary coincides with the African coast, and the northern boundary is closed by land.

The figure above shows the model domain and the model results of temperature for July 1996.

The bathymetry used was interpolated to the model grid using GEBCO (1 minute resolution). The model was initialized using GDEM (Generalized Digital Environmental Model) data and spun up over 8 years using climatological monthly means of atmospheric forcing data. The model was then run using a mixture of climatological (cloud cover from Comprehensive Ocean-Atmosphere Data Set (COADS)) and precipitation from Legates and Willmott (1990) and synoptic atmospheric fields from ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts).

Surface relaxation with 50 days decorrelation time for salinity and temperature was used in the experiment. On the open boundaries we apply a relaxation of temperature and salinity to monthly averaged climatologies produced by GDEM.

The Indonesian Throughflow (INTF) is a system of surface currents flowing from the Pacific to the Indian Ocean through Indonesian sea. The INTF plays an important role in the meridional transport of heat in the climate system, it originates from the warm-pool of the Pacific and enters into the colder waters of the South Equatorial Current (SEC) of the Indian Ocean. Net transport between Australia and Indonesia is 12

Sverdrup and it is included in the model.

The freshwater flux from Brahmaputra, Ganges, Irrawaddy, Salween, Mahanadi, Krishna and Godavary into the Bay of Bengal; Indus, Tapi, Narmada, Euphrates and Tigris into the Arabian Sea is included in the model, using monthly averages from the UNESCO (1993) database. The freshwater flux is treated as a negative salinity flux.

A 10 year simulation simulation experiment, 1992-2002, was done.

2 Model Results and Validation

2.1 Indian Ocean Surface Circulation

In this part of the validation we have focused on the circulation influenced by the monsoon seasons and therefor concentrate our analysis in the area north of 20°S. In the figure below, we see a summary of the surface circulation as reported by previous investigators.

SC, Somali Current; EACC, East African Coastal Current; EMC, Eastern Madagascar Current; SCC, Southern Counter Current; SEC, Southern Equatorial Current; IMC, Indian Monsoon Current, INTF, Indonesian Throughflow.

The most striking effect of the monsoon winds is the reversal of the Somali Current (SC) which flows northward during the SW monsoon and southward during the NE monsoon.

2.1.1 Bay of Bengal

The Bay of Bengal is an enclosed tropical basin under the influence of monsoonal winds and freshwater inflow. Four major gyres which have previously been reported (Varkey et al. (1996), Vinayachandran and Yamagata (1998)) in the Bay of Bengal have been simulated.

Haugen et al. (2002) claimed in the abstract of the article that G4 was "not previously reported" and that it was anticyclonic. Both of these things are wrong. G4 is cyclonic and G2 is anticyclonic through the year, while G1 and G3 change the direction from summer to winter. G1 is also being better resolved in our model compared to the model from Haugen et al. (2002), because of the higher resolution.

2.1.2 Arabian Sea

The figure above shows two anticyclonic gyres simulated in July; The Great Whirl (GW), the 500 km wide anticyclonic eddy located between 52°E and 57°E and the Southern Gyre (SG), located in the area 0°-5°N, 50°E. Haugen et al. (2002) called both of these gyres cyclonic, which is incorrect. Compared to WOCE Indian Ocean Expedition, our model resembles the gyres well.

2.2 Transport

Volume transport has been computed for selected sections passing through the major currents simulated by the model, and validated with in situ or model data whenever available. Total transports are calculated as the difference between the transport in and opposite to the reference direction. Positive Sv represents either eastward or northward transport.

The figures above show the timeseries of volume transports calculated for sections through the Indian Monsoon Current, Southern Equatorial Current, Equatorial Jet, Great Whirl, Somali Current, Indonesian Throughflow and East Indian Coastal Current.

2.2.1 Indian Monsoon Current

The figure above shows the volume transport calculated for the section 2° - 6° N at 80° E for the upper 300 m. The IMC indicates an average eastward transport of 10 Sv during the SW monsoon which is in agreement with Vinayachandran et al. (1999). The westward transport of the NMC during the NE monsoon is 20 Sv, 5 Sv higher than in the simulations done by Haugen et al. (2002). Reason for this might be that because of the more freshwater input in the Bay of Bengal (compared to Haugen et al. (2002)), more water is being transported by the NMC. Schott et al. (1990) reported a westward flowing NMC of 10.4 in January/February 1992 which is in agreement with our results.

2.2.2 Southern Equatorial Current

The volume transport for the SEC was calculated for the section 10° - 20° S at 63° E for all the layers. The SEC flows westward with an annual mean transport of 36 Sv integrated over all layers for the 6 years, which is in agreement with the mean of 37 Sv calculated over the 5 years (Haugen et al., 2002). The transport is normally strongest during the monsoon winds. Maximum transport of 54 Sv was observed in 1994 during July. The SEC has been observed with transports between 33 and 39 Sv during the NE monsoon (Wyrтки, 1971), which is within the range of our simulations.

2.2.3 Equatorial Jet

The equatorial section, between 2° S and 2° N at 80° E, shows the mean volume transport during the SW monsoon 14 Sv and during the NE monsoon 13 Sv. The mean during the SW monsoon is lower than Wyrтки (1973)'s estimates of 22.5 Sv, but the transport during the NE monsoon is more in the range of Wyrтки (1973)'s estimates of 14.

2.2.4 Great Whirl

The volume transport for the GW was calculated at section capturing the north-south flow at 8° N between 50° and 55° E. The northward flow has an average volume transport of 60 Sv over the whole water column, and 40 Sv in the upper 100 m. This compares well with results from Fischer et al. (1996).

2.2.5 Somali Current

The seasonal reversing Somali Current flows northward during the SW monsoon with a monthly mean volume transport of 21 Sv which is in agreement with Schott et al. (1990). Woodberry et al. (1989) reported a peak transport in August of 20.5 from their model simulation which also compares well with our results. During the NE monsoon an averaged southward transport of 10 Sv is observed.

2.2.6 Indonesian Throughflow

The volume transport for the INTF was calculated at section 8° - 20° S at 116° E for the upper 600 m. The INTF transport varies between -7 and 25 Sv, with the net transport roughly 10 Sv, which is in agreement with Vranes and Gordon (2005). McDonald and Wunsch (1996) obtained an estimated mean ITF transport of 10 ± 10 Sv, which is also consistent with our mean.

2.2.7 East Indian Coastal Current

The volume transport for the EICC was calculated at section 80° - 83° E and 13° N. The seasonal reversal can be seen from this section as southward during the SW monsoon and northward during the NE monsoon. The northward volume transport is observed to be 6.8 Sv in the upper 500 m which is in good agreement with Shetye et al. (1996)'s hydrographic data, which showed a transport of 7.7 Sv. The southward transport is between 5 and 15 Sv.

2.3 Water masses

The model reproduces all the characteristic water masses in the Indian Ocean well at all layers. Meridional and zonal sections of temperature and salinity have been plotted to study the model's ability to reproduce the observed water masses in the Indian Ocean. The major differences in temperature and salinity from month to month are observed in the surface. The sections have been validated using available in situ observations from the World Ocean Circulation Experiment data (WOCE) and Physical Oceanography Research Division (Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California, San Diego, see http://sam.ucsd.edu/vertical_sections/ind_sections.html).

2.3.1 SST and SSS

Surface temperature and salinity during February and July from the model (unfortunately we could not convert from the i- and j-index to lon and lat).

The sea surface temperature (SST) and sea surface salinity (SSS) are in good agreement with in situ data. The surface salinity for February shows the westward penetration of the low-salinity water from the Bay of Bengal to the southern Arabian Sea, and salinities down to 33.7 psu are simulated off the southern coast of west India, consistent with in situ data. In the northern part of Bay of Bengal salinity is 30 psu, 1 psu lower than in previous simulations done by Haugen et al. (2002), due to higher resolution and more freshwater input. Also, due to the higher resolution, salinity is 37 psu in the northern part of Arabian Sea, consistent with the in situ data.

At 30°S most of the Indian Ocean surface water is tropical, having uniformly high temperature around 25° which corresponds well to Reverdin and Fieux (1987) results from XBT sections. SST cools by 2° - 3°C from May to September throughout most of the northern Indian Ocean, which is partly due to area becoming cloudy and windy with the onset of the SW monsoon (Godfrey, 1995). Our simulations show a

cooling in the SST by 2° - 4°C from February to July.

Along the Somali coast and the western part of the South India the SST is low in July as a result of upwelling. Between Indonesia and Australia the SST is 30°C , 1°C higher than in the simulations done by Haugen et al. (2002), due to the transport of the warm INTF water from the Pacific Ocean.

2.3.2 Antarctic Ice

Seasonal ice conditions in Antarctica are shown in the figure below.

In the summer (Mars) the sea ice does not extend far beyond the Continent, but during late winter (October) it covers an area of the size of the Continent. Compared to Tomczak and Godfrey (1994) and to images provided by *National Snow and Ice Data Centre, University of Colorado, Boulder*, our model is doing well in reproducing the ice coverage.

2.3.3 Vertical sections of the temperature and salinity

The temperature profile to 700 m depth and a cruise track from a cruise which was done in February 2004 are shown in figures below.

Figure 6: Temperature section from XBT data along GoodHope I. The dashed isotherms represent the subsurface axis of the STC (blue- 10°C), SAF (red - 6°C) and APF (white - 2°C).

and the temperature profile for the same section from our model data:

The resemblance between the model data and the cruise data is good considering that the resolution in that domain is 40 km from our model, which is not sufficient to resolve all mesoscale processes like the eddies. From the observation data we see two structures from 36°-40°S, Agulhas current and one eddy (*GoodHope I Oceanographic Report, 2004*), while we only see the Agulhas current from our results. The Antarctic Circumpolar current is being resembled well from the model data between 60° to 80°S.

Next we studied the sections along 8°N, 32°S, 60°S, 90°E, 115°E and 9°N and the results were compared to World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) and to the previous model results.

1.) 8°S

The two upper figures show the WOCE sections of salinity and temperature, and the two lower figures show the HYCOM sections of salinity and temperature.

By comparing observations and model data, we can conclude that we have a problem with too fresh water in the mixed layer. The saline water coming from northwest (from the Arabian Sea) is not being reproduced by the model correctly. The salinity from our model is in the depth 0-400 m 0.1-0.3 psu lower than from the WOCE data. The problem might be that the Arabian Sea is not saline enough in our model and this can be linked to the GDEM data, that the model was initialized from. That is why we also plotted the same section using GDEM data and the plots are shown below.

As we assumed the problem can be linked to the GDEM data. We observe that the water coming from the Arabian sea is too fresh, even 0.3 psu lower than from the WOCE data. The solution to this problem might be to initialize the model from different data sources, that is why we also plotted the same section using Levitus data.

In this case the usage of Levitus data for the initialization would be better than GDEM data. The water coming from the Arabian Sea has the salinity 35.4 psu in the mixed layer which is in agreement with WOCE data. The water coming from the east, the INTF, is also better resembled with the salinity below 34 psu. The salinity and the temperature are also in better comparison to WOCE data in the deeper layers.

2.) 32°S

In the equatorial region the South Indian Central Water (SICW) has been reproduced in our simulations between 0-500 m depth. SICW is simulated with the temperatures between 9° and 24°C and salinities of 34.8-35.5 psu, with highest salinities in the western part part of this section. Toole and Warren (1993) reported that at the African coast there is a shallow lens of water warmer than 20°C . This was also observed in the western part of the surface layer in our simulations, in agreement with Wyrтки (1971) temperature plots.

In the intermediate levels, the low-salinity signature, 34.4-34.6 psu, of Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) is well developed along our section.

Below 1500 m depth, salinities as high as 34.7 psu have been observed along the section, in agreement with Haugen et al. (2002).

3.) 60°E

In the northern Indian Ocean the Arabian Sea-high salinity water (ASW) mass has been simulated in this section. The ASW, with salinities up to 36.8 psu, is a mixture of Persian Gulf Water (PGW) and Red Sea Water (RSW) and results from excess of evaporation over precipitation in the Red Sea and Persian Gulf. The main impact of these distributions is felt at intermediate levels. ASW spreads southward and is simulated down to 5°N with salinities of 35.2 to 36.4 psu and temperatures between 11° and 27°C consistent with in situ data. In the equatorial region the Indian Equatorial Water (IEW) has been reproduced in our simulations. IEW is observed between 5°N and 20°S , with salinities of 34.6-35 psu, and temperatures between 8° and 25°C .

The Red Sea Gulf Intermediate Water (500-1500m) is simulated down to 5°S with salinities between 34.8 and 35.4 psu and temperatures between 5° and 13°C .

4.) 90°E

The low-salinity Bay of Bengal Water (BBW) has been simulated in this section. The decrease in salinity from 34.5 psu at 5°N to 32 psu in the northern part of the bay is seen. The BBW influence extends well into the tropics and is simulated down to 10°-15°S, which is in agreement with Wyrski (1971) and WOCE data.

In the intermediate layer, the Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) with salinities of 34.6-34.8 psu, is observed south of 15°S. The Red Sea Persian Gulf Intermediate Water is simulated down to 8°S with salinities between 34.9-35.3 psu, and the temperature between 5°-11°C.

Below depths of 1500 m the Circumpolar Deep Water has been simulated, with salinities between 34.6 and 38 psu. Corresponding temperatures range between 0° and 3°C, which are also reported by Rao and Griffiths (1998).

We conclude that the simulation in this section using HYCOM is good.

5.) 115°E

The Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) is the deep ocean circulation current extending from the sea surface to depths of 2000-4000 m. It is stretching between 50° to 60° S. The ACC is being correctly reproduced in our model, coming from the south, with the temperature between -2° - 3° C and salinity 34.2 to 34.5 psu. Another current coming from the north, is the Leeuwin current. It is a warm ocean current that flows strongly southwards along the Western Australian Coast, before turning eastwards at Cape Leeuwin and continuing into the Great Australian Bight where its influence extends as far as Tasmania. This current is clearly shown in our figures stretching to 40° S and down to 300 m depth, which is in good agreement with WOCE data.

6.) 9° N

The WOCE section used for validating 9° N section shows that the temperature is well simulated. The salinity also compares well, however in the mixed layer the simulated salinity is 0.4 psu less than seen from the WOCE data. Again, this problem is related to GDEM, since we can observe from the figures below that the salinity is too fresh, in some parts of the surface layer it is even 0.8-0.9 psu lower compared to the WOCE data.

As earlier, we plotted the Levitus data for this section to compare the two different data sets.

The conclusion is the same as for the 8°S section. The Levitus data would be better to use in this case as the initialization data set. In the mixed layer the salinity is only 0.1-0.2 psu lower compared to WOCE data and the temperature is 29°C which is in good agreement with insitu data. Also in the deeper layers the temperature and salinity are being resembled better than from the GDEM data.

2.4 ENSO Events

From simulated SLA and SSTA in period 1992-2002 we identify one year, 1997, with unusual cooling in the east and warming in the west, which coincide with the negative Southern Oscillation Index (SOI) and El Nino years. In the plots below we compare the sla and ssta from a unusual year 1997 and normal year 1998.

The plots above show the simulated SLA for November 1997 (left plot) and the observed SLA for November 1997 (right plot).

High negative SLA are identified during 1997. These negative anomalies first appear in June off Sumatra. The drop in SLA suggests increased upwelling of cold deep water, this is also seen in the figures of the SSTA below. SLA increases and penetrates northwestward and is observed above 20 cm are in the model results which is in agreement with the altimeter results and also with Webster et al. (1999). Our model resembles the altimeter data better than the simulations done by Haugen et al. (2002) did, especially in the domain 20° - 30° S, because of the resolution which is twice as high in that region and also use of HYCOM (better representation of different dynamical regimes in the mixed layer) instead of MICOM.

In the figures above, cooling is simulated off Sumatra during June and during the following months this cooling intensifies and migrates toward the equator along the Indonesian coastline. The strongest events indicate a cooling of 3° - 4° C.

At the same time as the cooling in the east, the western Indian Ocean experiences a warming of 1°C during the unusual year.

With this warming, SLA increases, and higher than normal positive SLA are simulated. Between 5° - 12°S there is "ridge" with amplitudes above 20 cm in November 1997 extending between the coast of Africa and almost across the whole Indian Ocean, tilting slightly southeast. This ridge was also identified by Webster et al. (1999).

3 Conclusion

The HYCOM has been implemented and validated. The model is more complete and complex than previous models and has proven to reproduce the general ocean circulation, water masses, and volume transports for selected currents well compared to observations and previous model results. Exception are some sections around equator where we have too fresh water in the surface layer compared to insitu data and we connect this problem to the initialization from the GDEM data. By plotting the sections from the Levitus data, we found out the the use of this data set would be better than the GDEM. If it is better for the whole model domain, requires further investigation.

All the four gyres were recognized in the Bay of Bengal during the southwest and northeast monsoon and their directions and locations compare well to the previous results.

We identified year 1997 as an unusual year with the cooling in the east and warming in the west, which coincide with the negative Southern Oscillation Index and El Nino Years.

To complete the validation of the HYCOM model, the last step will be to compute the correlation coefficient for the selected latitudes between the observed and the simulated SLA.

References

- Bleck, R. (2002). An oceanic general circulation model framed in hybrid isopycnic-cartesian coordinates. *Ocean modelling*, 4:55–88.
- Fischer, J., Schott, F., and Stramma, L. (1996). Currents and transports of the Great Whirl-Socotra Gyre system during the summer monsoon, August 1993. *JGR*, 101:3573–3587.
- Godfrey, J. e. a. (1995). The role of the Indian Ocean in the global climate system: Recommendations regarding the global ocean observing system. *Background Rep.*, (6).
- Haugen, V., Johannessen, O. M., and Evensen, G. (2002). Indian Ocean: Validation of the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model and ENSO events during 1958-1998. *JGF*, 107(C5):doi 10.1029/2000JC000330.
- Legates, D. and Willmott, C. (1990). Mean seasonal and spatial variability in gauge-corrected, global precipitation. *J. Clim.*, 10:111–127.
- McDonald, A. and Wunsch, C. (1996). Indonesian Throughflow influence on the global general circulation. *US WOCE Implementation Report*, (No.8):23–25.
- Rao, T. S. S. and Griffiths, R. C. (1998). Understanding the Indian Ocean: Perspectives on oceanography.
- Reverdin, G. and Fieux, M. (1987). Sections in the western Indian Ocean-Variability in the temperature structure. *Deep Sea Res.*, 34:601–626.
- Schott, F., Swallow, J., and Fieux, M. (1990). The Somali Current at the equator: Annual cycle of currents and transports in the upper 100 m and connection to neighbouring latitudes. *Deep Sea Res.*, 37:1825–1848.
- Shetye, S., Gouveia, A., Shankar, D., Shenoi, S., Vinayachandran, P., Sundar, D., Michael, G., and Nampoothiri, G. (1996). Hydrography and circulation in the western Bay of Bengal during the northeast monsoon. *JGR*, 101:14011–14025.
- Tomczak, M. and Godfrey, J. S. (1994). Regional Oceanography : An Introduction. *Pergamon*, (422).
- Toole, J. and Warren, B. (1993). A hydrographic section across the subtropical south Indian Ocean. *Deep Sea Res.*, 40:1973–2019.
- UNESCO (1993). United Nations Educational and Scientific and Cultural Organization. *Discharge of Selected Rivers of the World*, 1, 2 and 3.
- Varkey, M., Murty, V., and Suryanarayana, A. (1996). Physical Oceanography of the Bay of Bengal and Andaman Sea. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: An annual Review 1996*, 34:1–70.
- Vinayachandran, P. N., Masumoto, Y., and Yamagata, T. (1999). Intrusion of the southwest monsoon current into the Bay of Bengal. *JGF*, 104:11077–11085.
- Vinayachandran, P. N. and Yamagata, T. (1998). Monsoon response of the sea around Sri Lanka: Generation of thermal domes and anticyclonic vortices. *JFO*, 28:1946–1960.
- Vranes, K. and Gordon, A. L. (2005). Comparison of Indonesian Throughflow transport observations, Makassar Strait to eastern Indian Ocean. *JRL*, 32:doi:101029/2004GL022158.
- Webster, P., Moore, A., Loschnigg, J., and Leben, R. (1999). Coupled ocean-atmosphere dynamics in the Indian Ocean during 1997-98. *Nature*, 401:359–365.
- Woodberry, K., Luthe, M., and O’Brien, J. (1989). The wind-driven seasonal circulation in the southern tropical Indian Ocean. *JGR*, 94:17985–19002.
- Wyrtki, K. (1971). Oceanographic Atlas of the International Ocean Expedition.
- Wyrtki, K. (1973). An equatorial jet in the indian ocean. *Science*, 181:262–264.